

MASS MEDIA AND SOME RECOMMENDATIONS FOR ELECTION IN VIETNAM

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Abstract: In the era of information booming with the robust development of the Internet and social networks, the mass media plays an important role, especially in the election. In this article, the author mentions the role of the mass media with the election in Vietnam and gives out some recommendations for the use of the mass media in the election in Vietnam.

Keywords: mass media, election, Vietnam.

I. INTRODUCTION

Vietnam, undergone more than 30 years of national renewal, and over 30 years of education and training Mass media from its inception with its first types and forms has a close relationship with politics. Politics with rich and diverse activities is an important source of information for the work of journalists. In contrast, the mass media participates and has an increasingly powerful influence on political processes and political activities. The power of mass communication lies in the fact that it creates public opinion, guides and directs public opinion; on the other hand, it significantly affects the formation of guidelines, policies and timely countermeasures of the ruling classes. Besides, the process of democratizing social life has created conditions for the mass media to assert its relative independent role.

In elections, the mass media is the bridge between candidates and voters. Through mass media, voters learn about candidates, and candidates create images and prestige in public. Moreover, the mass media also orients the masses in the midst of a flood of information, which acts as a “filter” for candidates, helping voters to choose those who are worthy and exclude those who are not qualified.

In Vietnam, the role of the media is also mentioned often in elections, but in reality, its participation is still very limited and has not brought into full play the potential and advantages of mass media. Therefore, the study of mass media and its significance in the election in Vietnam will provide suggestions for the use of mass media in the election in Vietnam.

II. CONTENT

1. Mass media

The concept of communication is derived from Latin: *commune* means common or community. Its connotation is the content, the method, the way, the means to achieve mutual understanding between individuals and individuals, individuals and social communities. In English, communication means *communication*, i.e. communication, propaganda, announcement, information, etc. Thus, *communication* is essentially a process of exchanging messages between members (groups of people) in the society to achieve mutual understanding and connection.

The audience and scope of communication activities are of many types. It could be an individual, a collective, in different large and small scopes. In which, mass media is a new and modern expression of communication activities. *Mass* here is the dissemination of information with a wide scale and scope of impact. It can transcend national and national frameworks, affecting the whole region or the world. Thus, mass media is first and foremost dissemination of information to the mass. But to achieve that it must resort to the corresponding means of communication. That is the mass media.

Thus, the concept of mass communication includes the connotation of two concepts of *mass information* and *mass media*. Accordingly, mass communication is the transmission of messages that are popular in society widely and openly through mass media.

Target audience of mass media: First of all, it is the public, a part of the population of society or a large social community of a country, region or the whole world that the mass media are aimed at influencing or trying to absorb into its sphere of influence. This is also the main object that powerful actors always have the ambition to dominate and impose their will. Accordingly, the mass media is a means for political power-holders to influence the public, thereby realizing the purposes and interests of their class.

2. Mass Media with Election in Vietnam

2.1. Role of mass media in elections in Vietnam

Election plays an important role in the political life of each country, is the basis for determining the legitimacy of state power agencies, the method for the people to select delegates and implement their mandate. It is also an important method through which the people control state power and assert their right to mastery. With the motto of building a state of the people, by the people, for the people. One of the prerequisites to ensure that the State is truly of the people, by the people, because the people are the people must have the right to freely choose and elect truly deserving delegates to join the state apparatus.

In the election of deputies to the National Assembly and People's Councils at all levels, the mass media plays an important role in the success, by propaganda work to make the whole Party, people and army clearly aware of the purpose and role of the Party. The role, meaning and importance of this political event is to select and elect worthy and representative delegates to represent the will, aspirations and mastery of the people in the National Assembly and Council at all levels for the new term, actively contributing to the construction, consolidation and improvement of the rule of law State of the people, by the people, for the people, under the leadership of the Communist Party of Vietnam, specifically:

Firstly, making the whole Party, the people, the whole army well aware of the purpose, role, meaning and importance of this political event is to continue building, consolidating and perfecting the socialist Vietnamese rule of law state of the people, by the people, for the people.

Secondly, raising awareness for cadres, party members and people of all walks of life about the Party's viewpoints and lines, the State's policies and laws on election.

Thirdly, strengthening the leadership and directing role of Party committees at all levels on election work, ensuring the promotion of democracy and the centralized and unified leadership of the Party in cadre work. Making all citizens firmly grasp the rights, obligations and responsibilities in building a clean, strong, effective and efficient state, to participate voluntarily, actively and proactively for election to be the festival of the whole people.

2.2. Election through mass media in Vietnam

With the purpose of raising awareness about the meaning and importance of the election, creating unity of thought, politics and action among cadres, party members and people to successfully organize the general election of deputies to the National Assembly and People's Councils at all levels and the mass media have completed their tasks.

Along with organizing a conference to contact voters, it is necessary to pay attention to the form of election campaigning through the mass media, such as radio, television, print newspapers, online newspapers, websites of election organizations to publish action plans and brief biographies of National Assembly candidates and congressmen in accordance with the provisions of the Law on Election of Deputies to the National Assembly and People's Council, ensuring fairness among candidates.

In Vietnam, the 2015 Law on Election of National Assembly deputies and People's Council deputies stipulates that election campaigning through the mass media is as follows:

- “1. National Assembly candidates shall present to voters their expected action plans if elected as National Assembly deputies when giving interviews on mass media in the locality where they stand for election on the National Election Council's website on election of deputies to the National Assembly.
2. Candidates for People's Council deputies shall present to voters their expected action plans if elected as People's Council deputies when giving interviews on local mass media and on the Election Commission's election website (if any).
3. The National Election Council and the Election Commission shall direct the agency managing the website to strictly comply with the provisions of law on posting election campaigning content.
4. Provincial-level People's Committees shall organize the publication of action plans of candidates for National Assembly and People's Council candidates on local mass media. [1]

3. Some suggestions for using mass media in election in Vietnam

Like many other countries in the world, election activities in our country also play a very important role in the socio-political life. It legitimizes state power and the existence of a democracy. Immediately after declaring the birth of the Democratic Republic of Vietnam, despite many difficulties, President Ho Chi Minh and our Party and State rushed to prepare for the general election on January 6, 1946.

In our country, due to the characteristics of the political system, the state is organized according to the principle of “unification and assignment and coordination” among state power agencies. Accordingly, “The National Assembly is the highest representative body of the people, the highest organ of state power of the Socialist Republic of Vietnam”, this was clearly stated in the 1992 Constitution. Also, the National Assembly election is the most important election in our country, it promotes democracy the most and also attracts a large number of people to participate. As soon as the 12th National Assembly election took place on May 20, 2007, 99% of voters nationwide went to the polls.

To prepare and organize each election to ensure the promotion of democracy, lawfulness, safety, thriftiness and truly a festival of the whole people, it is necessary to have the whole apparatus including Party organs, the State, the Fatherland Front, all levels, branches and the whole society. In which, it must be mentioned the significant contribution of the news agencies and the press. However, in elections for the People's Councils at all levels, due to taking place only in a limited area, such as districts (districts), communes (wards), townships, etc., so the participation of the mass media is not much, because the candidates mainly meet directly voters in the residential community there. Therefore, here only consider and evaluate the mass media mainly through the National Assembly election.

The mass media, with a sense of responsibility and enthusiasm, have actively participated in information and propaganda work over the years, contributing to the success of the elections from the central to the local government. However, the reality also shows that the mass media in our country has not really brought into full play its potential and has not been assigned a more worthy task, especially during the election campaign. In general, election campaign propaganda is limited in both content and form.

The mass media including television stations, radio stations, newspapers, etc. mainly just try to do well (in fact did quite well) propagandize for the people to understand the meaning and importance of the election. The National Assembly, to disseminate the main contents of the election law, on the position and role of the National Assembly and its deputies; about the rights and obligations of citizens, etc. However, it is almost not interested in providing information about the candidate to the voters, if any, it is only very poor information provided by the agencies in charge of the election. Therefore, it is a common situation today that voters still actively vote but paradoxically they know almost nothing about the people they elect. They rely on only a few lines of sketchy background information, a few sentences summarizing the general program of action at the polls to decide their vote, and then forget the name of their chosen representative right after

First of all, it is possible to allow candidates to advertise themselves on television (local or national) or on radio, newspapers, etc. This will allow candidates to get closer to the public and show their inherent strengths, especially on television because this is the most popular audio-visual medium.

With the current development of information technology, it is possible to set up common websites for candidates or for each candidate with a data bank of biographies, actual work achievements, action programs, etc. Voters who want to find out which candidate can find their name in a general list, then press “ok”, then a series of information about that candidate with different aspect will respond to all information needs of voters. The same can be applied to the automated telephone service, which, although not as useful, meets the needs of those who do not have access to the Internet.

However, the information of these two forms must be verified by a national election commission to avoid bias and fraud.

In addition, the mass media themselves must provide daily updates on the candidates, can provide objective evaluation opinions, and point out the candidate's strengths and weaknesses to help voters make easier and more accurate choices. Because not all voters are qualified and knowledgeable enough to get a good look at a candidate, even if they already know about their agenda or achievements. However, this is a very sensitive issue due to the “pen-bending” power of the mass media. Therefore, to ensure democracy, fairness and equality, it is necessary to study effective implementation options under the leadership of the Party and the management of the State.

In addition, it is possible to organize live televised press conferences with the volunteer participation of candidates (because any candidate who does not participate will lose their points invisibly). In which, the candidates answered not only journalists' questions but also voters' questions by calling directly or sent online. This forces candidates to be more accountable for what they say and also helps voters better understand who represents them.

The above are just some small suggestions, offering some new directions to help the elections in our country maximize the political positivity of the people and at the same time select people with real talent into the state apparatus. Moreover, because in our country there is no “run-for-election campaign” but only “election campaign”. Therefore, in order to implement the above proposals, there must be a clear mechanism to comply with the laws and rules of election campaigning.

III. CONCLUSION

The mass media plays an important role in the election, in the transmission of information, the mass media not only provides voters with basic knowledge and useful information, but it also helps voters to get the best judgment for your choice.

With such a great role, mass communication becomes an indispensable political technology, it can be affirmed that it is the most effective political technology, with such a great role, applied to Vietnam in the new conditions has great significance, because we are building a socialist rule of law state, owned by the people, by the people for the people, a state with its social criticism function.

REFERENCES

- [1] Law on Election of Deputies to the National Assembly and People's Councils 2015